

UNIBAP

SpaceCloud[®]

SPACECLOUD CLOUD
COMPUTING AND IN-
ORBIT DEMONSTRATION

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Agenda

- Intro
- Look at a background to the mission
- Spacecloud
 - HW
 - OS / Robustness
 - FW
- Some of the applications

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Wild Ride – Dauntless David

Goals

- Test application development in the SpaceCloud stack and SpaceCloud FW
 - Operating between several companies
- Understand impact of apps and framework in LEO conditions
- Develop necessary components for integrating this on the ION craft
- Development time of 3 months

Spacecloud

HW

iX5 or iX10

OS

SpaceCloud OS (SCOS) with
SafetyChip/SafetyBoot

Linux data processing on Ubuntu Server (x86)
and FreeRTOS

FW

- Dockerized deployment
- HW abstraction for apps

gRPC

Containerized
applications

SpaceCloud

SpaceCloud HW: iX5 series

Compute device	Theoretical Peak Performance
Quad core, 64-bit x86 CPU (AMD Jaguar) with AVX vector instructions	40 GFLOPS
AMD Radeon GPU	87 GFLOPS
Intel Movidius Myriad X Vision Processing Unit	4 TOPS
Microsemi SmartFusion2 FPGA	72 DSP cores + fabric
Storage with redundant boot (through SafetyBoot mechanism)	2 x 128 GB M.2 SATA SSD (SLC Nand flash memory type)

System setup

SpaceCloud OS

- Based on Ubuntu 18.04
- With SafetyChip/SafetyBoot
- FPGA Drivers
- Optimized drivers for GPU
- SDKs for connected hardware (none in this case)
- Package of software compiled for this platform

Robustness

- Safetyboot
 - Boot from ssd0/ssd1 or redundany backup option
 - Controlled from the MCU boot flagged from the OS
- SafetyChip
 - Watchdog functionality
 - Optional state tracking from the MCU
 - Chanins of watchdogs
- Middleware and hardware checks to check functionality of execution hosts
 - I.e. run test program on movidus before execution to make sure it has a valid state

Spacecloud FW

Saraniaapp

- Use a series of neural networks to efficiently find moving airplanes in 8kx10k pixel tiles
- Input is a tiled map of data
- Output is a tightly cropped image with position in kmz format
 - Can be visualized like this

Spacecar

Examples of other apps

- ML based ship detection
 - Myriad deep learning inference
- Video compression
 - OpenCL optimized
- Hyper spectral image compression (CCSDS-123.0-B-2)
 - Multi core cpu implementation
- FDL Worldfloods
 - Myriad deep learning inference
- ESA scientific workloads
 - Tensorflow lite CPU ML
- Max power test
 - All execution hosts
- Systems application
 - FDIR tests
 - Disk check tests
- PUSopen
 - Connectivity from spacecloud to other hosts on satellite or ground

Thanks!